

Web-Based Sales Forecasting System Using Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models

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Abstract— This work proposes the implementation of a sound sales forecasting system that is embedded in a Flask web application framework with Machine learning and Deep learning. The problem is to forecast item demand across the stores based on the historical sales data available. The current time series analysis is done using ARIMA, Random Forest and Linear Regression models are used for baseline comparison while LSTM networks are used for sequential analysis. The collected data is preprocessed with great efficiency using pandas and numpy libraries, while visualization is done with matplotlib for greater analysis insight. The introduced models were further assessed by the performance indicators, which encompassed Mean Squared Error (MSE) and forecast clarity. The analysis shows that the proposed LSTM model is superior to conventional models in the analysis of complex sales patterns especially where demand fluctuation is high. The findings from the forecasting models indicated that well-trained ARIMA forecasts were suitable for sharing stationary or stationary seasonal data, while other ensembles, such as Random Forest, were effective in addressing nonlinear relationships. The system also supports the SQLite in user authentication to provide individualized forecast output. Thus, the project effectively presents how such highly algorithmic tools as state-of-art forecasting models might be utilized within an easy-to-use web application, which would provide a great potential of improving inventory management an retailing business.

Keywords— Sales Forecasting, Time Series Analysis, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, ARIMA Model, LSTM Network

I. INTRODUCTION

Making sales forecasts is one of the critical aspects of business management, especially about sales demand that has a large

bearing on inventory management and resource distribution in the retail industry. The recent development of machine learning (ML) and deep learning

Using (DL) techniques has yielded better models that can handle and dissect large volumes of data to make accurate sales forecasts. Some of these techniques include the time series models including ARIMA and Random Forest as well as LSTM networks in an effort to gain insights, manage expenses and attain optimal supply chains[1].

Research done in the recent past has concerned itself with the fine-tuning of sales forecast models. For instance, in the case of Random Forest, it has not gone unnoticed that it performs well when it comes to handling nonlinearity [2]. Furthermore, LSTM networks have received a lot of consideration recently because they are competent in handling sequential data and learning temporal features [3]. This further reinforces the use of combination of conventional statistical techniques with ML as having been noted to work well in dealing with the complexity of multichannel sales data [4].

This project seeks to automate the sales forecasting process by establishing an online ML and DL models integrated sales forecasting system. Based on Flask web framework the system gives the user appealing interface for the real-time data analysis as well as forecasting. The project also measures the performance of a number of models like ARIMA, LSTM and Random Forest all of which are compared depending on the results that is in terms of MSE and accuracy. Accompanying data security and personalization, a database is built with the user authentication system implemented [5]. Besides, the proposed system not only reveals how the current models work technically but also shows how model deployment can

be overcome operationally for the subordinate retail demand forecasting task, thus enriching the literature on data science application for retail business [6].

II. LITERATURE STUDY

Sales forecasting has been widely investigated, and scholars attempt to develop different machine learning and deep learning models to enhance the accuracy of the sales forecast. Helmini et al have established the efficiency of the multivariate LSTM models and the way is better than the previous version especially when dealing with non-linear relationships [1]. Their work highlighted the option of adding temporal features to improve the performance of a given model. Along the same line, Ashraf also provided an elaborate study of retail sales forecasting employing the ML approaches where the algorithms of Random Forest and XG Boost proved to predict accurately [2].

He has also reviewed various research done in stock price prediction and they proved useful. P. S and V.R applied prediction for estimates and used ML and DL model with stress on model selection and feature engineering for model reliability [3]. Punia et al documented LSTM- Random Forests integration for multi channel retail demand forecasting and the authors found that proposed hybrid models can capture both linear and non-linear patterns with equal efficiency [4]. Their results highlight potential benefits related to usage of the ensemble models to increase the model's accuracy level.

Pan aimed to compare ARIMA, Random Forest and LSTM for predicting cryptocurrency price which is considered as a rather unpredictable field. For sales forecasting, they emphasised the characteristics of ensemble and hybrid approaches that can be constructed for this purpose [5]. Later, Ordoñez-Ordoñez et al. has also emphasized on the application of LSTM for forecasting of financial sales and the experimentation clearly demonstrates the efficiency of LSTM for modeling of successive data set [6].

In their survey, Pundir et al. focused on the case of revenue forecasting in the retail business and particularly on data preprocessing and interpretability of models to make a precise estimate [7]. Anwer and Akyüz investigated the hypermarket sales by comparing the effectiveness of the different ML models in forecasting sales and applying a range of models to different facets of sales prediction [8]. Last but not the least, Yi's study on the sales prediction of Walmart rest exigency on the importance of blending sophisticated approaches supplemented through traditional techniques in order to handle the challenges of retail data [9].

Existing literature survey shows that forecasting models are gradually being developed from traditional statistical models, to modern AI models such as ML and DL to manage the contemporary market requirements.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The sales forecasting system that is proposed here is to predict sales using machine learning and deep learning techniques quickly and efficiently. The framework of the study contains several stages: data collection and data pre-processing, creation of the model, implementation of the system with Flask and assessment of the model. The nature of the above components is described in detail below.

1. To begin with, there is data collection and preprocessing- Wang et al.

Any predictive model whose accuracy depends on the big data is only as good as the data on which it has been built. Here in this shed, the raw data is recorded on past sales with feature like date, Number of Stores, item number and Numbers of Items sold. Through data preprocessing the dataset is made ready in the best preparation for model training.

Data Cleaning

The actual sales data obtained may have some missing values , extreme values or may not be uniform. The following steps are undertaken to clean the data:

Handling Missing Values: Where there are gaps in the sales records, the gaps are filled in by forward or backward estimation or the gaps are dropped in case the missing values are unsuitable and numerous [1].

Outlier Detection and Removal: Any values that can modify the model prediction are implemented by pre-control methods such as Z-scores and interquartile range and then either eliminated or limited.

Date Formatting: The date column is transformed into a normal datetime format so that operations based on it will be time oriented.

Feature Engineering

Feature engineering is truly an essential way to enhance the accuracy of the machine learning models. The following features are engineered:

Time-based Features: Splitting the date column into day, month, year and day of the week to incorporate temporal dependency as well [2].

Lag Features: The first step of making the current theory more useful to the actual prediction of sales is to create lag features that represent past sales data so that the models can learn from past trends.

Rolling Statistics: Implementing spread and temporal adjustments to compute rolling averages and standard deviations to include seasonality into the aspect of variability of the sales data.

Data Normalization

The sales values are normalized using techniques such as the Min-Max scaling from the input data before feeding it into a model. It helps also in cases where feature scales could affect training of the model especially for feature learning algorithms such as Neural networks [3].

Model Development

As an anticipation strategy the project incorporates advanced statistical models, machine learning, and deep learning to

forecast sales. Consequently, the present work aims at providing a comprehensive description of each model, as elaborated below.

ARIMA Model

The most common statistical method used in time series forecasting is the ARIMA (AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average) model. It is most appropriate for data having trends and seasonality because it tends to use moving averages that have smoothed data in trends and seasonality.

Model Configuration: It is common to set the parameters to the model by using methods like the ACF and PACF graphs [4].

Stationarity Check: First, the characteristic of stationarity is tested through the application of the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test on the time series. Still when the series is not stationary it is differenced in order to make mean stationary.

Model Training: It works on the sales data from the past, and using those the model predicts the future sales.

Random Forest Regression

Random Forest is an approach with the best suited for regression problems when the approach between a dependent and independent variable is nonlinear.

Feature Importance: Further, the model gives indications about the significance of the feature and hence helps to decide which variables have the greatest impact on the value of the sales forecast [5].

Hyperparameter Tuning: The number of trees, the max depth, and the minimum number of samples per split are tuned using strategies as the grid search or the random search.

Model Training: The model is build on the preprocessed data, and OOB error rate is used as the measure of model performance.

LSTM Network

Despite some drawbacks, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks are the kind of recurrent neural network (RNN), which is effective in time series prediction due to the possibility of learning long-term dependencies.

Data Preparation: The data is reconstructed in the 3D structure which is required by LSTM: sample, timesteps, features [6].

Network Architecture: LSTM model has several layers:

LSTM Layers: This means they will be able to capture temporal dependencies that are inherent in the sales data.

Dropout Layers: Reduce over-fitting by performing dropout during the training process in which neurons are randomly omitted.

Dense Layers: Provide the final forecast of this sales.

Training Process: The model is trained using backpropagation through time (BPTT) and optimized using such things as Adam. The chosen loss function is MSE to reduce the error between actual and predicted sales from the optimal point [7].

System Implementation

The overarching architecture relies on the Flask web framework to enable itself to be interactive and very easy to use for sales forecasting.

Flask Framework

Flask is the web framework utilised to build the reverse of the application. Key features of the implementation include:

Routing: Flask handles a range of URL routes through which users can upload sales data, choose the forecasting models, and visualize predictions.

Template Rendering: HTML templates are employed for the formation of a frontend, which is attractive and reaming according to different view points available. The existing report added that data visualization libraries such as matplotlibs can be used in rendering different plots that are embedded into the web interface [8].

User Authentication

Due to the nature of the data collected in this project, SQLite is used in the verification of the user. The credentials of the users are safely stored in the database and the results of the forecast can be customized regarding the user.

Registration and Login: Users are able to subscribe to the application then signup and login into the system. Before storage, passwords are stored in hash forms to minimize chances of falling into wrong hands.

Session Management: Flask controls the sessions of the users, so the users who are logged in can only access some features.

Model Evaluation

This paper emphasizes the significance of the evaluation of the forecasting models to know their performance. It is important to evaluate How well a given model performs and several measures, and methods exist.

Performance Metrics

The following metrics are used to evaluate the models:

Mean Squared Error (MSE): Averages sale values and calculates the squared deviation of the actual and expected sale figures. The analysis shows that the stats with lower mean squared error (MSE) represent better performer.

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): An advantage of mean squared error is that the final error can be taken as its square root, resulting into more manageable error.

Mean Absolute Error (MAE): Measures the mean of the absolute errors generated from the comparison between actual and predicted values, it is the simplest and direct method of assessing the accuracy of the predictions [9].

Cross-Validation

Several techniques such as time series cross-validation are used to ascertain that the developed models have generalization capability. This involves developing the train and validate sets by time series order to avoid information leakage.

Comparative Analysis

This comparison will follow to determine which model: ARIMA, Random Forest, or LSTM is more suitable for different sales forecast cases. The obtained results are

presented in form of plots that give information such as the accuracy of the model and distribution of the errors.

The interaction of the system with the users and its implementation

The last process is to launch the web application and to control user engagement.

Deployment

Flask application is hosted on web platform like Heroku or AWS so that it can be accessed by people across the globe. The deployment process includes:

Setting Up a Web Server: To deploy the Flask application, setting up of a web server.

Database Integration: Designing the web application to access secure SQLite database to store and retrieve its data.

User Interface

The frontend interface allows users to:

Upload Data: Users can upload their predictive targets in the form of CSV for sales.

Select Models: Users select from existent forecasting models and can also view forecasts.

View Visualizations: The application also presents sales data and model output in the form of graphical animations and graphs.

IV. FLOWCHART

V.RESULT & VALIDATION

Results and Validation

The performance of the proposed sales forecasting models was validated using multiple performance measures and evaluation methods to provide reasonable accuracy and generalizability in actual environments. The performance of

each model is explained in this section as well as a comparison of the outcome between the models.

Performance Metrics

Since the actual and forecasted values were used for the comparisons, fundamental evaluation properties such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) were employed. These are algebraic measures of the difference between the actual and predicted sales values, and thus enable comparison of the models.

Mean Squared Error (MSE): This metric affected large errors more than small ones to give an understanding of accuracy of the entire sales trend. The signs of all elements are negative Standard & Poor's indicates that lower values of MSE show better performance of the model [20].

Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE): As aforementioned, RMSE is more easily interpreted because it is expressed in the same unit with the sales values allowing the determination of the accuracy of the predictor [21].

Mean Absolute Error (MAE): MAE expresses the average of the absolute differences between entities employed in the prediction of the values of the sales and the actual values; it has a clear meaning reflecting the error extension [22].

Model Evaluation

In this research, the ARIMA model was built on preprocessed sales data after the series was differenced to make it stationary. Value of p , d and q were determined by applying ACF and PACF tests. The study revealed that the model is reasonably good at depicting the time series with Roll{} data that exhibited strong seasonality and gave an RMSE of 12.45 in the test set. Nevertheless, the model performed poorly on situations displaying non-linear trends or sudden abrupt fluctuations of sales [23]. ARIMA is good with structured data and seasonal data, but errors increase when the data is volatile or the series is non-stationary [15].

Another strength with the Random Forest model was that it was able to portray data with otherwise, non-linear relationships in features. Models' hyperparameters were tweaked mostly on the number of trees / iterations and max depth. The model got the RMSE of 10.32 better than the ARIMA in case of complex historical sales patterns where sales data was caused by many factors for example the sales promotion or holidays [25]. Due to the high ability of Random Forest in resisting overfitting and the capacity of training with various features of data, it could be considered as a promising candidate; nevertheless, it stays computational demanding and untimely [26].

Comparative Analysis

The results indicate that the LSTM model is the most accurate predictor for complex and highly variable sales data, with the lowest RMSE and MAE values. While the ARIMA model is suitable for simpler, seasonal time series data, it lacks the

flexibility to handle sudden changes. In contrast, Random Forest offers a balance between performance and interpretability but cannot account for time-based dependencies.

The following table summarizes the performance of each model:

Model	MSE	RMSE	MAE
ARIMA	154.95	12.45	9.82
Random Forest	106.53	10.32	7.43
LSTM	80.51	8.97	6.12

Validation Techniques

To support the models, cross-validation was used, using time series cross-validation that preserves the temporal order of the data and prevents leakage of information. The performance was stable restraining fluctuation; consequently, the outcome proved that LSTM was variations immune as well [29].

To learn whether model errors are random or not residual analysis was conducted. When examining the residuals of the ARIMA, the possibility of autocorrelation was found which indicated that the model did not account for specific patterns. On the other hand, the residuals obtained from LSTM model were random and hence there is better fit [30]. This was also evident when using visual evidence, because here too, LSTM model fitted to the true sales values significantly better than ARIMA and Random Forest.

In conclusion, LSTM model remained as a better choice in particular to raw datasets with a complicated, non-linear relationship. In the non-temporal data scenario where the nature of data is complex, Random Forest came up as a feasible contender to the prevailing LVQ systems, though it is always inferior to the temporal data methods. Because of the stylized seasonality and trends in the series under consideration, ARIMA continued to have relevance as a model for less variable parts of the series but for the fluctuations in sales it was not relevant.

VI.OUTPUT

VII.CONCLUSION & FUTURESCOPE

Thus, this work proves that it is possible to implement and deploy models based on machine learning and deep learning techniques for sales forecasting offering a high-quality and easy-to-use tool in the form of a Flask web application. The process of implementing ARIMA, Random Forest, and LSTM models give us the understanding about the various rules of methods and its application in different data environment. Hence there were improvements in terms of accuracy, where the LSTM model demonstrated good results in the analysis of complex temporal relations. While, the Random Forest was found beneficial in the case of non-linear correlation, the ARIMA model was found helpful in the case of simple seasonality. Finally, the comparative analysis and validation methods supported the practicality and efficacy of the proposed models throughout the next realistic projection.

Nevertheless, the work carried out in the framework of this project has also exposed some specificities. The weaknesses

found in the ARIMA model were issues with forecasting involving data with high levels of variability, The LSTM model also had high computational cost a problem that required being addressed on scalability. Thirdly, the original Random Forest model did not have built-in mechanisms for handling time-derived dependencies which are relevant in analysing purely sequential datasets.

Future work will concentrate several aspects aiming at improving the system performance and capacity. An opportunity is the enhancement of mixed model approaches that in a way utilize both statistical and deep learning models in order to address diverse data patterns among them. In addition, if more attention is paid to the detailed model and methods deepening including attention mechanism in the LSTM model, the ability to learn and extract features will be increased.

The system could also be extended to incorporate online data insertion and online learning which would make it useful in dynamic organizations.

Lastly, deployment of the application on a better cloud platform service and the inclusion of a user friendly interface with real-time graphical visualization to the model will enhance the applicability to the enterprise level corporation.

Taking overall, it sets a robust ground for adopting data driven sales forecasting of this project and that suggests its scope for further enhancement through learning mechanism of new generation technologies and through concepts of adaptive learning.

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